

TRANSFORMATION OF THE I-NOVEL IN MODERN JAPANESE LITERATURE

Petrosyan Naira

Senior Teacher Nordic International University

petrosyannairi1@gmail.com

Khaliyeva Gulnoz Iskandarovna

Professor, DSc, Head of World Literary studies Department, Uzbek State World
Languages University

Abstract: I-novel, which is based on confession, was developing from an unformed, vague literary phenomenon and by the middle of the XX century became one the most important, literary genre, and moreover, the main stream in the literary process of Japan. If the "essence" of I-novel works at first was concentrated only on the description of writers' truthful or quasi-truthful life events and situations, which was sharply criticized by Akutagawa Ryunosuke, then by the middle of the century the Japanese I-novel totally changed by Dazai Osamu works and characterized by deep psychologism, detailed author's introspection and self-esteem to the present day.

Keywords: I-novel, transformation, confession, self-esteem, reflection, Tayama Katai, Naoya Shiga, Akutagawa Ryunosuke, Dazai Osamu

The I-novel (《私小説》) is a literary genre that originated in Japan at the beginning of the XX century and used to describe a type of confessional literature where the events in the story correspond to events in the author's life. This genre was founded based on the Japanese reception of naturalism during the Meiji period, and later influenced literature in other Asian countries as well. This genre of literature reflects greater individuality and a less constrained method of writing.

The development and emergence of the I-novel genre in Japanese literature have its origins since the Heian period. Famous writers of this period created a huge amount of outstanding works, such as «The Diary of Lady Murasaki» (《紫式部日記

»), «The Tosa Diary» («土佐日記»), «The Mayfly Diary» («蜻蛉日記»), «The Sarashina Diary» («更級日記») and others. The authors wrote, appealing only to their own experience, not mentioning what they did not see or hear themselves: «My thoughts were flowing like in a dream-somewhere far, far away, and I stopped noticing what was happening around me, finishing taking notes of a certain day by this way» [1]. Thus, we can observe the syncretism and transformation of the rudiments of autobiographical works in the Middle Ages, and then the appearance in the early 20s of the twentieth century of the original confessional genre which is called I-novel [2].

The authors who wrote in this genre sought to display their inner life and events from their biography as honestly and realistically as possible, but attributing them to a fictional hero. This genre is characterized by a scrupulous description of the protagonist's inner experiences, the narrative is built around the memories and reflections of the narrator. The earliest works in this genre includes: «The Broken Commandment» («破戒») by Shimazaki Toson, «The Quilt» by Tayama Katai («蒲団») and his trilogy «Life» («生») – «Wife» («生») – «Family Ties» («路»), «A Dark Night's Passing» («路路») by Naoya Shiga, «No longer Human» («人間失格») by Osamu Dazai, «A Fool's Love» («痴人の愛») by Junichiro Tanizaki, «Confessions of a Mask» («假面の告白») by Yukio Mishima, «A Personal Matter» («個人的な体験») by Nobel Prize winner Oe Kenzaburo and many others[3].

Any work of art anyway is somehow I-novel. It reflects the reality passed through the consciousness, its experience, its attitude. Without the presence of the author's personality, a work of fiction is unthinkable. Apparently, the problem is only in the extent, in the breadth of generalizations, in the understanding of the typical [4].

The «I» as the only object of cognition and display, or the «I» as an instrument for cognition and display of objective reality - this is where the boundaries between I-novel and a work in which the protagonist is the author himself. This is exactly how Akutagawa Ryunosuke understood this problem [5]. Thus, we can conclude that

Akutagawa greatly influenced the rethinking of essence of the I-novel to his contemporaries.

Dazai Osamu (1909-1948) is considered to be the most talented I-novel writer of the XX century — a man whose life was full of tragedies. In the last period (1946-1948) of his work, Dazai Osamu was already a well-known and recognized writer, his stories were full of decadence, lack of faith and hopelessness. One of them is «No longer Human». Despite too many controversial opinions and literary criticism about this Dazai Osamu's story, the work has become a huge event and made a crucial difference in the literary world.

Dazai's contemporaries followed his tradition of I-novel in a new way, and thanks to Dazai's transformation of the I-novel it is one the most notable and famous genres in modern Japanese literature to the present day.

References:

1. Murasaki Shikibu. Dnevnik. [Murasaki Shikibu. Diary]. St. Petersburg, 2000. - p. 96. (in Russian).
2. Rekho K. «Vatakusi Shosetsu» // Kratkaya literaturnaya entsiklopediya. ["Watakushi Shosetsu" // Brief literary Encyclopedia]. - Moscow: 1962-1978. - p. 179. (in Russian).
3. Rekho K. Tayama Katay. Bol'shaya sovetskaya entsiklopediya [Tayama Katai. The Great Soviet Encyclopedia]. Moscow: Soviet Encyclopedia, 1978. - p. 113. (in Russian).
4. Lutskiy Aleksandr Leonidovich. Ekzistentsializm i yaponskaya literatura [Existentialism and Japanese Literature]. Dis. Candidate of Philology. Moscow, 1986. p. 168. (in Russian).
5. Interesnnyye mysli ob «ego-belletristike» [Interesting thoughts about «I-novel»]. Modern Japanese Novel, M., 1974. - pp. 86-110. (in Russian).